

Let's Smile at Each Other

In this year new,
Let's do one thing new.
Let's smile at each other
And walk miles together.

Telling life stories to each other,
Make happy each other.
Life is too short and there is so much to enjoy.
Why to criticise? Let's appreciate each other.

A word of praise will create wonders.
Ample bliss is there in enjoying them together.
Let's walk hand in hand.
Smiling at each other,
Let's make this short life long.

Who knows? When we will have a divine call?
Before it comes, let's enjoy this life with all.
Love everyone whoever comes in your way.
With your presence make their lives gay.

About the author: Dr. Balasaheb Ishwar Wakde has been working as an assistant Professor of English in MIT School of Computing, MIT ADT University, Pune, Maharashtra, India. He has authored books and published many research papers in national and international journal.